

partly into the middle portion of the flag leaf sheath and held there with scotch tape. At maturity, disease intensity (DI) was rated using a 0-9 scale. Zero indicated

no infection and 9 indicated complete flag leaf sheath discoloration and un-emerged panicles (Fig. 1).

Increasing N application significantly

increased DI in both varieties (Fig. 2). The regression coefficient (b) in both varieties was equal, indicating a similar trend. □

Reaction to rice tungro virus (RTV) complex as influenced by insect pressure

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We inoculated five IR varieties with 1, 5, 10, 20, and 30 *N. virescens* per plant to test their reaction to RTV complex. The

insects were allowed 4-d acquisition access time on plants infected with both rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). Test plants were planted singly in clay pots and enclosed in mylar cages. One month after planting, insects were allowed 24 h inoculation access time on the plants. The second youngest leaf from each plant was

sampled for RTBV and RTSV by latex test 1 mo after inoculation.

Infection with RTBV and RTSV increased in IR36 and IR42 when viruliferous insects/plant increased from 1 to 30. Only RTBV infection increased in IR50 and IR54, whereas an almost equal infection of both RTBV and RTSV, and RTBV alone was obtained in IR56 (see figure).

Varieties infected only by RTBV (IR50 and IR54) may not serve as virus source because the virus could not be recovered by the vector insect. However, these test varieties may not be immune to RTSV infection (see table). □

Percentage infection of IR varieties when inoculated with RTSV at 1 insect/seedling, IRRI.

Variety	Inoculated seedlings (no.)	Infected seedlings	
		No.	%
IR36	36	21	58.3
IR42	38	15	39.4
IR50	38	6	15.7
IR54	38	8	21.0
IR56	39	32	82.0
TN1	102	85	83.3

Reaction of IR varieties to RTV complex when inoculated with varying numbers of viruliferous insects per plant, IRRI.

Evaluation of National Screening Nursery (NSN) and international Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) trials for bacterial blight (BB) and stem rot (SR) resistance

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We evaluated NSN and IRON varieties for BB, kresek, and SR resistance in kharif 1980, 1981, and 1982.

Each variety was planted in two 5-m-long rows. Plants were inoculated with kresek at 20 d after transplanting (DT) and with BB at 45 DT. Inoculation was by cutting 5 cm of the upper leaves with a sickle dipped in inoculum prepared by soaking small pieces of naturally infected leaves in water for 20 min. Infection was scored on a 1-9 scale.

SR screening was done under natural incidence, and evaluated at maturity on a

1-5 scale.

BB intensity was high in most trials. SR incidence was high only in 1982. Resistant entries were selected and re-tested. Entries with consistent reaction to SR and BB for 2 yr or longer are given in the table.

Sixteen NSN and 14 IRON entries were consistently resistant. Resistant IRON entries BR171-2B-8, IR13420-6-3-3-1, IR19660-131-3-3-3-3, IR9763-11-

Summary of results of NSN and IRON evaluation against BB, kresek, and SR, Haryana, India.

Year	Trial	Test	Severity index		Entries (no.) showing rating							Total entries (no.)
					1	2	3	4	5	7	9	
1980	NSN-I	BB	6.6	High	1	—	26 ^a	—	28	180	33	268
	NSN-II				—	—	12	—	18	154	92	276
1981	NSN-I	Kresek	6.9	High	32	—	12	—	72	49	157	321
	IRON	BB	7.4	High	1	—	26	—	21	67	137	254
1982	NSN-I	BB	5.4	Moderate	39	—	69	—	68	106	54	334
		Kresek	5.8	Moderate	—	—	6	—	206	104	11	327
	IRON	SR	4.0	High	4	23	79	71	158	—	—	330
		BB	7.0	High	3	—	35	—	38	93	133	343

^aEntries resistant for more than 2 yr — NSN (resistant to BB and K): IET nos. 7061, 7100, 7338, 7349, 7393, 7419, 7420, 7421, 7431, 7434, 7447, 7662, 7707, 7736, 7752, 7753. IRON (resistant to BB): BR161-2B-53, BR161-2B-58, BR171-2B-8, IR134-20-6-3-3-1, IR19660-131-3-3-3, IR9763-11-2-2-3, IR17488-2-3-2, IR19661-23-3-2-2, IR17494-32-1-1-3-2, IR75-2878, IR50, IR54, DR55-9, MRC 603-383. NSN entries resistant to SR and BB for 2 yr: IET nos. 7753, 8169, 8175, 8195, 8197, 8259, 8303, 8319, 8322, 8325, 8327. NSN entries resistant to SR, kresek, and BB (1982): IET nos. 8140, 8145, 8353, 4141.

2-2-3, IR17488-2-3-2, IR19661-23-3-2-2, IR17494-32-1-1-3-2, and MRC603-383 were included in advanced breeding trials. In the NSN, 11 entries were resistant to SR and BB and 4 (IET8140, IET8145, IET8353, and IET4141) to SR, kresek, and BB. □

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Pest control and management INSECTS

Inheritance of virulence of the North Sumatra population of the brown planthopper (BPH) on IR42

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We studied the genetic nature of virulence of the North Sumatra (NS) BPH population. Nymphal development and adult longevity and maturity of the NS population, the Bogor population on Pelita I/1 that does not infest resistant rices, and their hybrid progenies were compared on IR42 seedlings.

The F₁ and F₂ hybrid progenies were obtained by heterogametic pairing of the NS and Bogor BPH populations. The backcrossed progenies were bred by crossing the F₁ with the NS or the Bogor population. Twenty 1st-instar nymphs and newly emerged brachypterous adult females were collected at random from each parental or hybrid population maintained on susceptible Pelita I/1, and placed in test tubes with 1- to 2-wk-old IR42 seedlings, 2 seedlings/tube. Nymphal development, and longevity and development of ovaries were recorded

Table 1. Nymphal development of the NS and Bogor populations and their hybrid progenies on IR42 seedlings, Jakarta, Indonesia.

Cross ^a	Nymphs tested (no.)	Adult emergence (%)	Developmental period of nymphs which became adults (d ± SD)	Growth index ^b
Female × Male				
NS × NS	20	80	12.9 ± 1.3	6.2
B × B	20	20	15.5 ± 0.6	1.3
NS × B	20	30	14.3 ± 1.5	2.1
B × NS	20	10	14.5 ± 2.1	0.7
(NS × B) ²	20	30	13.3 ± 0.5	2.3
(B × NS) ²	19	21	12.8 ± 1.0	1.6
NS (NS × B)	20	55	13.4 ± 2.4	4.1
B (B × NS)	20	35	14.4 ± 2.6	2.4

^aNS = North Sumatra population on IR42, B = Bogor population on Pelita I/1. ^b% adult emergence divided by mean duration of nymphal period in d.

Table 2. Longevity and maturity of adult females of the NS and Bogor populations and their hybrid progenies on IR42 seedlings, Jakarta, Indonesia.

Cross ^a	Females tested (no.)	Gravid females (%)	Longevity (d ± S. D.)
Female × Male			
NS × NS	20	90	16.0 ± 6.7
B × B	21	5	3.6 ± 2.7
NS × B	20	5	3.9 ± 4.0
B × NS	17	18	5.5 ± 6.1
(NS × B) ²	20	30	6.5 ± 5.8
(B × NS) ²	20	10	4.3 ± 4.5
NS (NS × B)	20	50	12.5 ± 9.5
B (B × NS)	20	25	6.3 ± 5.8

^aSee footnote, Table 1.

daily. Experiments were conducted at room temperature (25-30°C).

Parentage distinctly influenced nymphal development. Eight percent of the NS nymphs emerged as adults in 13 d. Only 20% of the Bogor population reached adulthood in 16 d. Development of the hybrid F₁ and F₂ nymphs from reciprocal crosses was similar to that of the Bogor population. When the F₁ with NS as maternal parent was backcrossed with the same population, nymphal development was intermediate between the NS and Bogor populations. However,